

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of new linearly fused 6-substituted-3,8-diacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indoles, their chemoselective bromination and synthesis of 3-thiazolylpyranoindoles

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Manuscript received 1 December 2003, accepted 17 May 2004

When 1-substituted-3,6-diacetyl-5-hydroxy-2-methylindoles 1(a,b) were reacted with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of 2-methylpiperidine produced new 6-substituted-3,8-diacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indole-2-ones 2(a,b). Then these compounds 2(a,b) were chemoselectively brominated with bromine in chloroform to generate exclusively, 6-substituted-3-bromoacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-8-acetyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indole-2-ones 3(a,b). Compounds 3(a,b) were then refluxed in dry ethanol with thiourea to secure 6-substituted 3-(2-aminothiazol-5-yl)-8-acetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indole-2-ones 5(a, b). Similarly, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone 6 was heated with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of 2-methylpiperidine to get 3-acetyl-4-methyl coumarin 7. The structures of all these newly synthesised compounds have been confirmed by spectral and analytical data and the compounds have been screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Indole derivatives constitute an important class of heterocycles because of their diverse pharmacological properties¹⁻⁵ like antimicrobial, anticancer, antihypertension, anti-inflammatory etc. Similarly, coumarins are also endowed with interesting antibacterial, anticoagulant and rodenticidal activities². In the light of above biological activities, it was envisaged to construct the α -pyrone ring on the benzene part of the indole moiety leading to the synthesis of novel linearly fused α -pyranoindole derivatives.

Literature survey revealed that the synthesis of 3-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin³ has been realised by the reaction of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with diketene in boiling toluene in very poor yield. Though, Knoevenagel condensation was utilised for the synthesis of 3-acetylcoumarin⁴ by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of piperidine, the same reaction conditions failed to produce the title compounds when ethyl acetoacetate was reacted either with 3,6-diacetyl-5-hydroxy-2-methylindoles⁵ 1(a,b) or with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone 6.

Brown and Mihm⁶ have reported that 2-methylpyridine is a stronger base than pyridine presumably due to electron donating inductive effect of methyl group. Hence, we also thought on same lines and used in this reaction 2-methylpiperidine which is a stronger base than piperidine

Scheme 1

yielding first time the desired hitherto unknown novel linearly fused 6-substituted-3,8-diacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indol-2-ones 2(a,b) in good yield. Similarly,

the above cited modified reaction condition was also first time applied for the condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone **6** with ethyl acetoacetate to generate the required 3-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin **7** in 75% yield which was otherwise obtained earlier in very poor yield (20%) by diketene route³. In conclusion, we found first time a novel method for the synthesis of 3-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin **7** and linearly fused 3,8-diacetylpyrano[6,5-*f*]indoles **2(a,b)** in very good yield. Further, the pyranoindoles **2(a,b)** were chemoselectively brominated at C₃-acetyl group to obtain the required 6-substituted-3-bromoacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-8-acetyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indoles **3(a,b)**. This is in conformity with our earlier reports⁷. The unreactivity of C₈-acetyl function of the diacetylindoles **2(a,b)** towards bromine could be related to the reduced double bond character of this group due to canonical structure **4(a,b)** wherein the π electrons of indole nitrogen are delocalised on the oxygen of this C₈-acetyl group. The 3-bromoacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-8-acetyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indoles **3(a,b)** were heated at reflux with thiourea in dry ethanol to obtain hitherto unknown 6-substituted-3-(2-aminothiazole-5-yl)-8-acetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indole **5(a,b)** in good yield. Further, the structures of all these compounds were confirmed on the basis of their spectral and analytical data.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of compounds prepared

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	Analysis (%): Found (calcd)		
				C	H	N
2a	153–154	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ NO ₄	73.64 (73.98)	5.26 (5.13)	3.43 (3.75)
2b	118–120	64	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ NO ₄	74.28 (74.40)	5.82 (5.46)	3.44 (3.61)
3a	238–239	46	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ NO ₄ Br	61.22 (61.07)	4.36 (4.01)	3.28 (3.09)
3b	286–287	44	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ NO ₄ Br	61.46 (61.81)	4.82 (4.32)	3.24 (3.00)
5a	264–265	54	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	67.28 (67.11)	4.38 (4.45)	9.64 (9.78)
5b	232–233	43	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	67.32 (67.70)	4.73 (4.77)	9.38 (9.47)
7	104–105	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂	77.54 (77.40)	5.68 (5.41)	–

Scheme 2

Biological evaluation (antimicrobial activity) :

All the newly synthesised compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity *in vitro* at doses of 100 μ g in 0.1 ml of DMF against the Gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive bacterium *Micrococcus* using Norfloxacin as standard and for their antifungal activity *in vitro* against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* using Griseofulvin as standard. DMF was used as solvent control, nutrient agar was used as culture medium and the method employed was cup-plate method⁸. The zone of inhibition was measured in mm and was compared with standard drugs. Compound **2b**, **5a** and **5b** displayed higher activity against *Micrococcus* while compounds **2a**, **2b** and **5a** showed higher activity against *E. coli*. Compound **5a** displayed higher activity against *Penicillium* and *A. niger*. All other compounds exhibited moderate to weak inhibitory activities against both bacteria and fungi except compound **2b**, which was inactive towards both the fungi.

Table 2. Antimicrobial screening results of new compounds synthesised

Compd.	Zone of inhibition			
	<i>Micrococcus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Penicillium</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
2a	++	+++	++	++
2b	++	+++	–	–
3a	++	+	++	++
3b	++	++	++	++
5a	+++	+++	+++	+++
5b	+++	+	++	+

– = Inactive (< 12 mm) Norfloxacin +++ (25 mm)
 + = Weakly active (12–16 mm) Griseofulvin +++ (30 mm)
 ++ = Moderately active (17–21 mm)
 +++ = Highly active (22–30 mm)

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Nicolet-Impact 410 spectrometer. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Av Brucker 300 MHz and AMX 400 MHz spectrometers, chemical shifts being expressed in δ ppm downfield from TMS. Elemental analysis was performed with Heraeus CHN rapid analyzer.

6-Substituted-3,8-diacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[6,5-*f*]indole-2-ones (**2a,b**) :

1-Substituted-3,6-diacetyl-5-hydroxy-2-methylindoles **5(a,b)** (5.7 mmol) were heated with ethyl acetoacetate (5.7 mmol) in presence of 2-methylpiperidine (5 drops) in catalytic amount on oil bath at 228–230°. The heating was con-

tinued for 6 h and the reaction was monitored by TLC. After cooling to RT, the residue was triturated with benzene-petroleum ether (40–60°). The solid obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Compound **2a** : ν_{\max} (KBr) 1628 (C₈-C=O), 1631 (C₃-C=O), 1708 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 2.34 (3H, s, C₈-COCH₃), 2.60 (3H, s, C₃-COCH₃), 2.62 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 2.73 (3H, s, C₇-CH₃), 7.24 (1H, s, C₅-H), 7.33–7.67 (5H, m, C₆-phenyl), 8.01 (1H, s, C₉-H); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 14.2 (C₇-CH₃), 17.3 (C₄-CH₃), 34.0 (C₃-CH₃), 35.2 (C₈-CH₃), 106 (C₅), 108 (C₉[b]), 121.2 (C₅[a]), 122.3 (C₇), 127.5 (C₄-phenyl), 129 (C₃-phenyl), 132 (C₂-phenyl), 133 (C₈), 137 (C₁-phenyl), 149 (C₄[a]), 157 (C₁[b]), 150 (C₄), 176 (C₂-CO), 194 (C₈ and C₃-CO).

6-Substitued-3-bromoacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-8-acetyl-2H-pyrano[6,5-f]indoles **3(a,b)** :

To a well stirred solution of 6-substitued 3,8-diacetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2H-pyrano[6,5-f]indole-2-ones **2(a,b)** (1 mmol) in chloroform (50 ml), bromine (1 mmol) in chloroform (5 ml) was added with magnetic stirring in about 10 min. The mixture was stirred for 0.5 h. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40–60°).

Compound **3a** : ν_{\max} (KBr) 1706 (C₂-C=O), 1690 (C₃-C=O), 1732 cm⁻¹ (C₈-C=O); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 2.36 (3H, s, C₈-COCH₃), 2.65 (3H, s, C₇-CH₃), 2.82 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.52 (2H, s, C₃-COCH₂Br), 7.30 – 8.09 (7H, m, Ar-H).

6-Substitued-3-(2-aminothiazole-5-yl)-8-acetyl-4,7-dimethyl-2H-pyrano[6,5-f]indoles **5(a,b)** :

A mixture of 6-substitued 3-bromomethyl-4,7-dimethyl-8-acetyl-2H-pyrano[6,5-f]indoles **3(a,b)** (1 mmol) and thiourea (1.5 mmol) in dry ethanol (50 ml) were heated under reflux for 5–6 h. The product was treated with aq. ethanol (50%), sodium bicarbonate solution (10%) and finally washed with water. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol.

Compound **5a** : ν_{\max} (KBr) 3434 (NH₂), 1712 (C₂-C=O), 1628 cm⁻¹ (C₈-C=O); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 1.6 (2H, br s, NH₂) disappeared on D₂O exchange, 2.53 (3H, s, C₈-COCH₃), 2.64 (3H, s, C₇-CH₃), 2.85 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 7.25

(1H, s, C₅-H), 7.68 (1H, s, C₉-H), 7.34–7.68 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.03 (1H, s, C₅-H thiazole). MS (m/z, relative intensity) 429 (M⁺,1), 414 (2), 388 (1), 374 (74), 359 (100), 331 (10), 317 (10), 303 (4).

3-Acetyl-4-methylcoumarin **7** :

o-Hydroxyacetophenone (1 g, 7 mmol) was heated with ethyl acetoacetate (0.91 g, 7 mmol) in presence of catalytic amount 2-methylpiperidine (5 drops) on oil bath at 228°. The heating was continued for 2–3 h, after cooling to RT, the residue was poured on ice water. The solid separated was filtered and washed thoroughly with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. ν_{\max} (KBr) 1678 (C₃-C=O), 1709 cm⁻¹ (C₂ lactone-C=O); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 2.48 (3H, s, C₃-COCH₃), 2.61 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 7.34–7.75 (4H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank S.I.F., I.I.Sc., Bangalore, R.S.I.C., Chandigarh, U.S.I.C., K.U.D., for spectral analyses. The authors Mr. S. R. Pujar and D. S. Donawade thank Karnatak University, Dharwad for providing University Research Studentship.

References

1. A. H. Abadi, *Arch. Pharma.*, 1998, **22**, 352; E. B. Skibo, C. Xing and R. Dorr, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **44**, 3545; K. S. Pitzer and P. John, PCT Int. Appl. WO 0018769 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 260669); B. Zang and F. Pelaez, US patent 6,081,597 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 266695); R. W. Stevens, PCT Int. Appl. WO 9965104, (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1999, **130**, 153572).
2. Feuer, *Adv. Med. Chem.*, 1974, 10.
3. R. N. Lacey, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1954, 816.
4. Knoevenagel, *Brichte*, 1898, **31**, 730.
5. G. S. Gadaginamath and R. R. Kavali, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1998, **9**, 39; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 178.
6. H. C. Brown and X. R. Mihm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1723.
7. G. S. Gadaginamath, A. S. Shyadligeri and R. R. Kavali *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1998, **37**, 1137.
8. F. Kavanag, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic Press, New York, 1963, p. 125.